

Deliverable D1.5

Project communication strategy - update and evaluation

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1. Executive Summary

This document presents the findings and outcomes of the evaluation of the GDI project communications, as defined in [D1.2 GDI Project communications strategy](#). It presents qualitative and quantitative data to measure the effectiveness of GDI communications and provides a series of recommendations and updates on the strategy.

The evaluation shows that the project has effectively implemented the D1.2 GDI Project communication strategy with content across communications channels, including website, newsletters and social media. Based on the results of the evaluation, four key areas for improvement were identified:

- Increase the frequency of social media posting and optimise the strategy
- Expand the newsletter outreach
- Monitor the engagement metrics
- Highlight GDI outputs through engaging video content

This strategy focuses on project communications and is distinct from D1.3 (Wider communications strategy), which specifically addresses citizens and healthcare professionals.

2. Contribution towards project outcomes

With this deliverable, the project has reached or the deliverable has contributed to the following project outcomes:

[Select 'Yes' (at least one) if the deliverable contributed to the key result, otherwise select 'No'. For more details of project outcomes, see [here](#)]

	Contributed
<p>Outcome 1</p> <p>Secure federated infrastructure and data governance needed to enable sustainable and secure cross border linkage of genomic data sets in compliance with the relevant and agreed legal, ethical, quality and interoperability requirements and standards based on the progress achieved by the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 2</p> <p>Platform performing distributed analysis of genetic/genomic data and any linked clinical/phenotypic information; it should be based on the principle of federated access to data sources, include a federated/multi party authorisation and authentication system, and enable application of appropriate secure multi-party and/or high-end computing, AI and simulation techniques and resources.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 3</p> <p>Clear description of the roles and responsibilities related to personal data and privacy protection, for humans and computers, applicable during project lifetime and after its finalisation.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 4</p> <p>Business model including an uptake strategy explaining the motivation, patient incentives and conditions for all stakeholders at the different levels (national, European, global) to support the GDI towards its sustainability, including data controllers, patients, citizens, data users, service providers</p>	No

(e.g., IT and biotech companies), healthcare systems and public authorities at large.	
<p>Outcome 5</p> <p>Sustained coordination mechanism for the GDI and for the GoE multi-country project launched in the context of the 1+MG initiative.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 6</p> <p>Communication strategy – to be designed and implemented at the European and national levels.</p>	Yes
<p>Outcome 7</p> <p>Capacity building measures necessary to ensure the establishment, sustainable operation, and successful uptake of the infrastructure.</p>	No
<p>Outcome 8</p> <p>Financial support to the relevant stakeholders to enable extension, upgrade, creation and/or physical connection of further data sources beyond the project consortium or to implement the communication strategy and for capacity-building.</p>	No

3. Methods

The European Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) project aims to realise the 1+MG initiative's ambition of creating a data infrastructure that will enable secure access to genomics and corresponding clinical data across Europe. At the time of writing this deliverable, the project involved a consortium of partners from 24 European countries, four of which joined the project in 2024, and two infrastructure organisations.

The project published a [Project communication strategy \(D1.2\)](#) in M6 of the project (April 2023) which outlined a strategy to communicate GDI project outputs. This document evaluates this communication strategy and updates it to maintain a high level of awareness and trust by the main stakeholders, notably European citizens, data holders, healthcare professionals, researchers and public health authorities.

To update the communications strategy, we build on:

- the experience and skills of the [ELIXIR External Relations team](#)¹
- lessons learned from the delivery of the [ELIXIR Hub portfolio of projects](#)²
- the specific project needs, defined by the interaction with three Pillars, different WPs, the coordination team, project partners, and other projects and initiatives, such as the B1MG project and 1+MG Initiatives.

4. Description of work accomplished

4.1 Communications evaluation and future work

4.1.1 Website

The GDI website is the primary communication channel for the GDI project. It provides information about the project, including news releases, events and deliverables. An initial version was available in time for project kick-off and updated in September 2023 (M11).

The website includes information about the vision of GDI, how the project is organised and who is involved. Importantly, it explains the context of the project, providing links to related actions including B1MG, 1+MG, the Genome of Europe and the European Genome Dashboard.

The number of unique visitors to the GDI website during the first 24 months of the project was nearly 14,000. The number of tracked page views was over 24,000. The top three viewed pages of the GDI website are the project participants page, outputs and how GDI is organised. This shows that visitors to the website are usually looking for information on the GDI project's organisation and its outputs.

¹ <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/who-we-are/hub>

² <https://elixir-europe.org/about-us/how-funded/eu-projects>

Focusing on the news content page, the top three most viewed news items on the GDI website are the news on the 1+MG Framework and roadmap, the eighteen-month highlights of the project, and the addition of new countries to the project. This indicates that the GDI project audience is interested in the news on project expansion and outcomes.

GDI website's top three visited page	
Page	Unique pageview
/about/participants	1,012
/outputs	856
/about/how-organised	772
GDI website's top three viewed news	
The 1+MG Framework and Roadmap is launched	635
Highlights from the first 18 months of the European Genomic Data Infrastructure Project	389
New countries join the European Genomic Data Infrastructure project	363

4.1.1.1 Website content

As of M24 of the project, the GDI project website has seven news articles on project highlights and two Stakeholder Forum event announcements. All project deliverables and milestones and past newsletters are archived on the website to demonstrate project outputs.

In the coming months of the project, ELIXIR Communications Officers will continue to work with other Work Packages to identify newsworthy project updates for the GDI website. The focus of the remaining two years of the project will be the timely and clear dissemination of project outputs.

4.1.2 GDI Newsletter

The GDI newsletter for external stakeholders has been released quarterly since April 2023. Up until October 2024 (M24 of the project), the GDI project has accumulated 266 newsletter subscribers and released six regular newsletters and one special issue highlighting the outcome of the GDI Stakeholders Forum.

The average open rate of the newsletters is 58.153% and the average click rate is 20.40%, demonstrating a good level of engagement. Analysing the top five clicked links in each newsletter

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issue, the most viewed contents are GDI project news updates and deliverables. GDI-supported publications and recommended reads and events in the newsletters also accumulated numbers of clicks and views. These indicate that the newsletter subscribers are interested in receiving project outputs from the newsletter.

The GDI newsletter is one of the main means to share project outputs. Sharing GDI project news in the newsletter can bring traffic to the GDI website and increase views of project news and other website content. In the remaining months of the project, the Communications Officers will continue to collect news and deliverables of the project as well as recommended publications and events that are of interest to project partners.

4.1.2.1 Newsletter content

The newsletter will continue to present news and updates on the project as well as activities and achievements. In addition to the original content planned in D1.2 Project communications strategy, future newsletter issues will focus more on deliverables and milestones as well as project supported publications to enhance the dissemination of project outcomes.

4.1.2.2 Subscribers

The newsletter is open to subscription from any individual and the project is focused on a broad demographic of scientists (e.g. biologists, data scientists, social scientists and policymakers). Therefore the content will be understandable and accessible, with the information provided to link to further technical details.

To increase subscribers of the GDI newsletter, each issue has been and will continue to be promoted on social media with a link to the newsletter and a subscription link.

4.1.2.3 Archive

All GDI newsletter issues are archived on the [GDI website](#).

4.1.3 Social media

The project's social media strategy focuses on community building and networking. The Twitter/X account ([@GDI_EUproject](#)) and LinkedIn account ([Genomics Data Infrastructure](#)) have been set up and are managed by ELIXIR's Communications Officers within the External Relations team. The main audiences targeted by social media are project partners, bioinformaticians, research scientists, infrastructure providers, data generators, policymakers and funders.

The first posts were published in November 2022 when the project website was launched. At the time of writing this deliverable, there were 451 followers on Twitter/X and 1,545 on LinkedIn.

4.1.3.1 Posts engagement

In the first 24 months of the project, 112 tweets (including re-tweets) were published and 31 original LinkedIn posts were published. From September 2023, Twitter/X has stopped providing free analytics, therefore post impression and engagement numbers can't be accessed and only numbers of likes and retweets can be extracted. LinkedIn still provides comprehensive analytic data for social media posts engagements.

Here the examples of top-performing LinkedIn posts are shown below:

Table 1: Sample of GDI top performing LinkedIn posts

Date	Post / Link	Impression	Likes	Shares	Comments
2024-04-17	<p>🚩 The GDI project is proud to announce that four EU countries - Cyprus 🇨🇵, Hungary 🇭🇺, Malta 🇲🇹 and Romania 🇷🇴 - have officially joined the project!</p> <p>👏 The addition of Cyprus, Hungary, Malta and Romania's institutions to represent their countries in the GDI project is a significant milestone 🦶 in the project's progress towards creating an interoperable genomic data infrastructure across Europe.</p> <p>🎯 The participation of more EU countries in GDI is a step closer to support the ambition of the 1+MG initiative of realising the practice of genomic medicine across Europe.</p> <p>Read the news: https://lnkd.in/e8AHbYbE</p> <p>hashtag#1MGenomes</p>	4,619	126	26	1
2024-05-14	<p>🎉 Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI) is 18 months old!</p> <p>In the past 18 months, 👏 we've been working on technology deployment - with the release and deployment of the #GDISTarterKit and developing sustainability and governance for the infrastructure.</p> <p>👉 Looking forward, the GDI project will work at the technical, operational and governance levels to develop and expand the 1+MG infrastructure.</p> <p>Read the news ➡ https://loom.ly/SU2KeJo</p> <p>#1MGenomes</p>	3,568	76	17	3
2023-11-15	<p>🚩 The 1+MG initiative has launched the 1+MG Framework and Roadmap, which bring together recommendations, guidelines and best practices to realise the 🎯 hashtag#1MGenomes initiative's vision for 🔒 secure access to genomics and clinical data across Europe and provide a pathway for implementation.</p> <p>Read the news 🔗 https://loom.ly/a2JWbXM</p>	2,547	91	18	1

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European Research Executive Agency (REA), EU Digital & Tech					
2022-11-17	<p>🎉 Today, we are pleased to launch the new project funded by the European Commission under the Digital Europe Programme : Genomic Data Infrastructure (GDI)</p> <p>🌍 The GDI project involves a consortium of partners from 20 European countries and 2 international organisations.</p> <p>The project will work on providing the 🗄️ data infrastructure for the #1MGenomes initiative, including legal and ethical frameworks for cross-border access to sensitive data.</p> <p>🔗 Visit the project website and read the news release https://lnkd.in/e/z38DnZN</p>	2,341	124	54	7
2024-06-21	<p>The GDI project and the European Federation for Cancer Images (EUCAIM) have formally signed a memorandum of understanding! 🗋️</p> <p>Both EU projects share a commitment to enabling cross-border data access and analysis, fostering the development of machine learning and AI models for personalized medicine applications. We look forward to collaborating with EUCAIM to achieve cross-border data access and accelerate progress in machine learning and AI models for the healthcare system. 🍀</p> <p>Read the news: https://lnkd.in/d/HViuNVn</p>	2,257	58	8	0

4.1.3.2 Special campaign

At month 18 of the project, the communications team planned a social media campaign to highlight the achievements of the project. From May to July, nine tweets and LinkedIn posts have been published. The posts covered the importance of the 1+MG infrastructure, GDI's efforts in allowing access to synthetic data across national borders and testimonies from researchers from four GDI Nodes (Ireland, Portugal, Denmark and the Netherlands).

On LinkedIn, the special campaign has an average of 1746 impressions and 0.05 engagement rates, which is higher than the average LinkedIn engagement rate³. This shows the success of the special campaign on project highlights. In the coming months of the project, social media campaigns around topics such as the Stakeholders Forum and the GDI project video, planned under the D1.3 Wider Communications Strategy, will be created to boost the project's social media engagement.

³ <https://blog.hootsuite.com/average-engagement-rate/>

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4.1.3.3 Platforms comparison

From July 2023, there has been a drop in engagement on Twitter/X and an increase in LinkedIn. This is likely due to users leaving Twitter/X after numerous changes implemented on the platform, including paid subscriptions and limited tweets for unregistered users.

It is noticeable that the GDI project has more followers on LinkedIn (1,530) than Twitter/X (446), which is different from other EU projects coordinated by ELIXIR (e.g. B1MG had 615 followers on Twitter/X and 552 on LinkedIn; FAIRplus had 1,039 followers on Twitter/X and 416 on LinkedIn). This indicates that for the GDI project, more audiences are on LinkedIn than on Twitter/X and that the future focus of the GDI project's social media use should be more on LinkedIn.

The GDI project will continue to use both social media platforms to share the project outputs with a stronger focus on LinkedIn to feature longer blog style posts.

4.2 Dissemination evaluation

Dissemination is the process of ensuring all scientific outputs are openly available and in forms that are easily accessible, understandable and reusable. Dissemination fosters the use and uptake of results and outcomes. In contrast, communications covers the sharing and promotion of wider project efforts. Dissemination activities target audiences that are likely to use the results in their work, for instance, peers and experts in and outside of the project, including policymakers.

Communications activities target multiple audiences beyond the project consortium, including the media and the public. The dissemination activities described in D1.2 Project communications strategy include external events and publications.

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4.2.1 External events

To raise awareness about the main aim and outputs of the GDI project, project partners have attended key events organised by external parties or organisations. By presenting at external events, the relevant scientific communities will be able to use the results and outcomes of the project in their work.

In the D1.2 Project communication strategy, relevant conferences were identified as potential events for GDI partners. In the past 24 months of the project, project partners have attended and presented at over 50 conferences, external meetings and workshops, examples of five external events GDI project partners attended in 2024 are listed below:

Date	Event	Target groups	Objectives and outcomes
2024-06-10	ELIXIR All Hands Meeting 2024	Research communities	Organised a mini-symposium to discuss coordinating progress towards a Genomic Data Infrastructure
2024-05-30	1+MG Group meeting	EU institutions; national authorities	Receive updates from EC DGs, provide review of 1+MG and 1+MG implementation projects progress
2024-04-21	GA4GH Ascona Connect	Research communities	Presented GDI project and outlined discovery requirements in the Discovery workshop
2024-02-19	SupercomputingAsia 2024	Research communities	Introduced the work of GDI project to audiences and stakeholders outside of Europe
2024-01-25	Festival of Genomics & Biodata 2024	Research communities; industry	Presented GDI's ambition towards cross-border access to human genomes at scale for research and healthcare and collaboration with other EU projects.

At the time of writing, the GDI project partners are holding a workshop at ECCB 2024 to strengthen the research community's understanding of the efforts needed for building a European genomic data infrastructure. In the remaining months of the project, project partners are encouraged to continue to attend external meetings and disseminate the outputs of the project to be used in the relevant scientific communities.

4.2.2 Zenodo

Zenodo is used as a home for project outputs, such as deliverables, posters, presentation slides, training materials and other related documents. Up until October 2024, there are 34 documents uploaded to the GDI project's [Zenodo community](#) with a total number of 5,258 views and 7,006 downloads. The top three viewed documents are:

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Document	Date	Views	Downloads
GDI - D4.1: Helpdesk roadmap	08-Jun-23	399	289
European Genomic Data Infrastructure project (GDI) D8.4 Report on federated data access scenarios	02-Aug-23	378	397
First GDI/1+MG Stakeholders Forum - Presentations	11-Jan-24	354	416

ELIXIR Communications Officers will continue to make efforts to ensure these outputs on Zenodo are shared on the GDI website and social media. Dissemination will be facilitated by the use of appropriate metadata when uploading to Zenodo (e.g. grant agreement number 101081813, Digital Europe, ORCID IDs of the authors), which will improve FAIR metadata for findability, as well as project-wide aggregation by EC's OpenAIRE. Zenodo also provides the number of views and downloads of documents, which can be used to evaluate project dissemination progress.

4.2.3 Publication

Publication is one of the key dissemination activities as it can help increase awareness and publicity of technical knowledge resulting from project implementation. In the first 24 months of the project, project partners added manuscripts, preprints and peer-reviewed publications to the [GDI Dissemination activities tracker](#) and are encouraged to continue recording publications in the upcoming months of the project. In the first 24 months of the project, six publications were added to the dissemination activities tracker. The number of publications is not expected to be as high as other EU-funded research projects since the GDI project is focusing on implementation rather than research.

4.2.4 Tracking and monitoring

Dissemination efforts are the responsibility of all work packages, in contrast to communications efforts which fall primarily under WP1. All dissemination activities contributed by GDI partners will be added to the [GDI Dissemination activities tracker](#) by project partners.

As described in D1.2, the tracker is included in the project's monthly internal newsletter to remind project partners to record external activities where project partners have given a talk or presented a poster and the target audiences. While tracking dissemination activities is the responsibility of all project partners, the Communications Officers will help monitor and update the tracker based on project reporting and management board meeting updates when necessary.

5. Discussion

Based on the evaluation of communications and dissemination activities in the past 24 months, below are some improvements that could be implemented in the coming months of the project.

- **Increase the frequency of social media posting and optimise the strategy:**
Given the higher followers and engagement rates on LinkedIn, the project will continue to prioritise this platform and engage with project stakeholders by sharing relevant posts. In the remaining months of the project, the Communications Officers will also develop social media campaigns around critical deliverables and milestones in alignment with the news releases on the website.
- **Expand newsletter outreach:**
The Communications Officers will further promote newsletter subscriptions via social media, the website, and external events.
- **Monitor engagement metrics:**
In the coming months of the project, the Communications Officers will continue to track and analyse engagement metrics across all communications channels and adapt the communications strategy accordingly.
- **Highlight GDI outputs through engaging video content:**
As the project moves into its final two years, promoting project outputs becomes critical. Video is an impactful format to showcase technical milestones in an engaging way. Five short videos are currently planned:
 - Video demonstrating milestones 7 and 8 (M25)
 - Introduction to the 1+MG infrastructure (M30)
 - What 1+MG means for citizens (M30)
 - What 1+MG means for healthcare professionals (M30)
 - Video demonstrating the production system (M48)

6. Conclusion

The project communication strategy update focused on evaluating communication and dissemination activities in the past 24 months of the project. The project has effectively implemented the D1.2 Project communication strategy by maintaining high standard content across all communications channels, including website, newsletters and social media. The communications evaluation also shows that the GDI project has maintained high engagement and visibility on LinkedIn, which is the main social media platform of the project.

GDI project's dissemination activities have successfully reached the key stakeholders and targeted audiences in scientific and public sectors by participating in external events and conferences. The GDI Community on Zenodo is the main platform to publish project deliverables and milestones and has accumulated over 5,000 views and 7,000 downloads from the scientific community.

In the remaining 24 months of the project, ELIXIR's Communications Officers will work on improving the GDI project's communications and dissemination activities with a focus on the frequency of news updates, social media strategy, newsletter outreach and monitoring engagement metrics. ELIXIR's Communications Officers will continue monitoring and evaluating the effectiveness of this Communication Strategy update and adapt their approach when necessary.

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